

The Chemical Composition, Therapeutic Benefits, and Safety of Zamzam Water: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

Zamzam water, originating from the well in Mecca, Saudi Arabia, holds significant spiritual and health-related importance for Muslims worldwide. This systematic review synthesizes existing literature on its chemical composition, therapeutic benefits, mechanisms of action, and safety. Key findings indicate that Zamzam water contains elevated levels of essential minerals all within permissible limits set by international regulatory agencies like the World Health Organization (WHO) and the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA). Its alkaline pH and rich mineral profile contribute to its antioxidant properties, supporting hyperglycemia control, renal protection, cancer prevention, dental health, wound healing, and immune modulation. Despite concerns about heavy metals and nitrates, rigorous testing confirms its safety for consumption. Further research is needed to fully understand its unique characteristics and potential nutraceutical benefits.

Keywords: *Zamzam, antidiabetic, antidy lipidemic, antihypertensive, nephroprotective, cardioprotective.*

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Introduction

Water is fundamental to life, serving as a medium for physiological processes and maintaining overall health. Among various water sources, Zamzam water stands out due to its historical significance and reputed therapeutic properties. According to Islamic tradition, this holy water has been providing sustenance since the time of Prophet Ibrahim (Abraham) and his son Ismail (Ishmael), approximately 5,000 years ago (Bhardwaj, 2023).

The sterile and fungus-free Zamzam water well is located east of Al-kaa'ba, the Muslim prayer site, in Mecca (Makkah), Saudi Arabia. Millions of Saudi citizens and millions of foreign residents use Zamzam water as their primary drinking water for one to three consecutive months every year, and millions of pilgrims who visit Saudi Arabia each year also take it back to their home countries as presents for close friends and family. According to Islamic tradition, Prophet Ismail, peace be upon him (PBUH), was still a little boy when his mother, Siti Hajar, was traveling through the parched region of Saudi Arabia and struggled to obtain water for her thirsty infant. Siti Hajar jogged nonstop from Safa Hill to Marwa Hill till her seven runs were officially recorded. Then, with Allah's approval, the Prophet Ismail's feet struck the earth and sprang a spring known as Zam-Zam water. This spring never dries up and is constantly running (Wahyudi, et al., 2022).

Scientific studies have explored its mineral content, isotopic signature, radiological features, and biological effects, revealing intriguing insights into its health-promoting capabilities. This systematic review aims to consolidate evidence on the chemical composition, therapeutic benefits, mechanisms of action, and safety of Zamzam water.

Study Selection

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews (PRISMA) checklist was employed in the current study to furnish materials that encompassed data collection, problem determination, and analysis and interpretation (Page, & Moher, 2017). The search process was conducted to identify articles that assessed the chemical composition, therapeutic benefits, and safety of Zamzam water in databases such as PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Additionally, historical records and religious texts (e.g., Hadiths) were consulted. The search was conducted using the following keywords: Zamzam water, chemical composition, therapeutic benefits, safety, antidiabetic, nephroprotective, cancer prevention, complementary medicine, and alternative medicine, all without any time constraints. Furthermore, the references listed in all relevant articles were manually reviewed to identify additional potential literature in order to optimize the search integrity.

The authors of the study evaluated the eligibility of all retrieved articles for inclusion in our analysis. Using Mendeley software, duplicate identification and qualification evaluation were conducted on all articles identified in the database. Articles that were irrelevant, duplicate, overview, or letter to the editor were excluded. In the event that the full manuscript of the article is unavailable, the abstract will be employed. If the abstract fails to provide the necessary information, the article will be excluded from the study. The selection process of the searched articles is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Study Selection Procedure (PRISMA Flowchart)

Chemical Composition

The hydro chemical and microbial analyses of groundwater play a significant role in the evaluation of water quality (Tiwari, 2011). In Saudi Arabia, a significant number of individuals consume Zamzam groundwater (Shomar, 2012). The Zamzam well has been in use for approximately 4,000 years, as per Arab historians (Khalid, et al., 2014). The chemical composition of Zamzam water is deemed acceptable by the World Health Organisation (WHO) and the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) for drinking water, with the exception of total dissolved solids (TDS) (Donia, & Mortada, 2021).

Chemical Composition of Zamzam Water

The alkaline nature of the Zamzam water is suggested by its pH value. This could potentially account for the low concentrations of Ag, Al, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb, and Zn in the water of Zamzam (Shomar, 2012). Granite is the primary rock in the aquifer rocks of Zamzam water, as per the Saudi Geological Survey (Bhardwaj, 2023; Khalid, et al., 2014). The Zamzam water's alkaline pH is likely a result of its association with granitic environments (Koh, et al., 2008; Buil, et al., 2006). The elevated concentrations of Ca^{2+} , K^{+} , and HCO_3^{-} may be attributed to the alkalinity of the water and the relatively low total dissolved solids, which facilitate the dissolution of silicate minerals in the surrounding rocks (Koh, et al., 2008).

Several studies conducted by researchers using various methods of chemical analysis on Zamzam water have proven the presence of 34 elements in Zamzam water, with calcium, magnesium, sodium, and chloride present in higher concentrations than in natural water. The elements antimony, beryllium, bismuth, bromine, cobalt, iodine, and molybdenum were 23 less than 0.01 ppm. Only traces of

chromium, manganese, and titanium were detected in Zamzam water (Shomar, 2012; Al Doghaither, et al., 2021; Al Zahrani, et al., 2019) (Figure 2).

The hydro chemical analysis of Zamzam water indicates that it is sodium chloride water. The concentrations of the four hazardous elements, arsenic, cadmium, lead, and selenium, were significantly below the risk threshold for human consumption. Numerous experts assert that specific characteristics enhance the quality of Zamzam's water, including elevated calcium levels (Shomar, 2012; Khalid, et al., 2014; Ahmad, et al., 2018).

Figure 2. Chemical Composition of Zamzam Water

Source: Donia, & Mortada, (2021); Al Doghaither, et al. (2021); Bamosa, et al. (2013)

Note: ppm = part per million, ppb = part per billion

The final say on the percentage of arsenic in Zamzam water: Research was conducted on this subject, and the findings were inconsistent, particularly in relation to arsenic (Al-Barakah, Al-Jassas, & Aly, 2017; Al-Ansi, Othman, & Al-Tufail, 2011). In Zamzam water samples collected by pilgrims following their return from Mecca, Shomar discovered elevated levels of As, NO₃, Ca, and K (Shomar, 2012). BBC News reported in 2011 that the illegal sale of Zamzam drinking water, which was contaminated with arsenic, was occurring in UK shops (Donia, & Mortada, 2021). In contrast, the Saudi geographical survey asserts that it has a specialized centre (Zamzam Studies and Research Centre) that conducts analyses and monitors the properties of the Zamzam well (Hussain, & Al-Fatlawi, 2020). Researchers verified that the concentration of (As) was within the acceptable range as recommended by various committees (Alfadul, & Khan, 2011). Another researcher documented the acceptable levels of (As) and NO₃ in Zamzam water samples in accordance with local and international standards (Al-Barakah, Al-Jassas, & Aly, 2017). Zamzam water, which is consumed by millions of Muslims worldwide, has been the subject of numerous recent studies, which have contributed to the body of evidence

regarding its safety (Donia, & Mortada, 2021; Ali, Aminu, & Orode, 2024; Al-Barakah, 2016; Zergui, Aledeh, & Hamad, 2022).

Comparison of the Chemical Composition of Zamzam Water and Drinking Water

In one of the studies, it was found that one mineral in a single drop of Zamzam water has a unique significance that you won't find in any other water on this earth. If a single drop of Zamzam water is mixed with a thousand drops of regular water, the regular water will acquire the same quality as Zamzam water. Additionally, in some tests, the quality or components of Zamzam water cannot be changed, and science does not know the reason. Even recycling Zamzam water did not cause any change; it remained pure (Shomar, 2012). This indicates that there are clear differences between the components of Zamzam water and drinking water, as shown in the Table 1 (Khalid, et al., 2014; Alfadul, & Khan, 2011; El-Zaiat, 2007).

Table 1. Comparison between Zamzam Water and Traditional Bottled Drinking Water

| |
|--|---------------------|------------------------|--------------|--|
| | TDS | 452 | 1000 | |
| | pH | 7.21 | 7.73 | |
| | Conductivity(μS/cm) | 740 | 1390 | |
| | Total hardness | 228 | 300 | |
| | Calcium | 136 | 220 | |
| | Magnesium | 92 | 80 | |
| | Chlorides | 100 | 260 | |
| | Fluoride | 0.32 | 0.59 | |
| | Sulfates | - | 180 | |
| | Nitrates | - | 31.6 | |
| | Silica | 11.3 | 37.6 | |
| | Phosphate | 0.13 | 0.15 | |
| | Copper | - | 0.04 | |
| | Residual chlorine | 0.45 | Nil | |

Therapeutic Benefits

Numerous studies highlight the health benefits of Zamzam water across multiple domains: Figure 3.

Diabetes Management

Zamzam water significantly reduces hyperglycemia and improves insulin secretion both in vivo and in vitro. It stimulates hexokinase enzyme activity, promoting glycolysis and cellular glucose uptake (Wahyudi, et al., 2022; El Maleky, et al., 2021). Regular intake lowers hemoglobin A1c levels and mitigates oxidative stress in Type 2 diabetic patients (Khalid, et al., 2014 ; Al Zuhair, & Khounganian, 2006). When combined with a ketogenic diet (KD), Zamzam water further enhances its hypoglycemic effects, significantly reducing fasting blood glucose compared to KD alone or regular water consumption (AlJuwaie, et al., 2023).

Renal Protection

It normalizes kidney function parameters (urea, creatinine, albumin) and reduces oxidative stress biomarkers (MDA, NO) while increasing reduced glutathione (GSH) (Wahyudi, et al., 2022; El Maleky, et al., 2021). Its anti-inflammatory and anti-apoptotic effects protect against streptozotocin-induced diabetic nephropathy (Ali, et al., 2009). It was demonstrated that consuming Zamzam water decreases

serum uric acid levels, potentially preventing gout and kidney stones due to its alkalizing effect (Mahmoud, et al., 2020).

Cancer Prevention

Zamzam water demonstrates oncolytic action by modulating gene expression and reducing tumour size in colon cancer models. It increases lymphocyte populations within tumour tissue and elevates serum somatostatin levels, inhibiting tumour growth (Wahyudi, et al., 2022; Ali, et al., 2009; Siraj, et al., 2019). Experimental mice injected with azoxymethane (AOM) showed a significant reduction in tumour size after consuming Zamzam water daily for one month (Lutfiah, 2020). Arsenic in Zamzam water selectively targets cancer cells, sparing normal cells due to their stronger antioxidant systems (Mahmoud, et al., 2020).

Dental Health

High fluoride content (~0.59 mg/L) reduces the prevalence of dental caries, particularly in permanent teeth (Wahyudi, et al., 2022; Al Zuhair, & Khounganian, 2006). Children using Zamzam water exhibit the lowest decayed, missing, filled teeth (DMFT) scores due to its optimal fluoride concentration (~0.72 ppm) (Lutfiah, 2020).

Reproductive Health

Zamzam water activates aquaporins (AQPs) in the endometrium, enhancing fertility and supporting biochemical processes such as immunoglobulin formation (Wahyudi, et al., 2022; Ali, et al., 2009). Studies show substantial increases in endometrial AQPs (AQP2, AQP3, and AQP4) and the appearance of novel AQPs (AQP7, AQP9, and AQP10) after consuming Zamzam water (Ahmad, et al., 2018; Ali, et al., 2009). Lutfiah emphasized that Zamzam water stimulates stem cell differentiation in the endometrium, providing additional support for reproductive systems through its high calcium and magnesium content (Lutfiah, 2020).

Neurological Effects

Studies suggest that Zamzam water may enhance cognitive performance in healthy adults and older adults. Its antioxidant properties contribute to neuroprotection, potentially mitigating oxidative stress-related damage in neurons. However, concerns about heavy metal contamination, particularly arsenic and lead, raise questions about long-term safety (Abuelhaija, et al., 2023). Another study investigated the underlying mechanisms and proposed a neuroprotective effect of Zamzam against behaviours like anxiety and depression brought on by diabetes. These results point to a potential treatment approach for diabetic individuals who suffer from depression and anxiety (Taha, et al., 2023).

Lipid Profile Improvement

Studies indicate that Zamzam water reduces LDL cholesterol levels, especially when combined with a ketogenic diet. In rats fed KD for ten weeks, those consuming Zamzam water showed significantly lower LDL cholesterol compared to groups consuming ordinary water (AlJuwaie, et al., 2023). This effect may be attributed to its magnesium content, which activates lecithin cholesterol acyltransferase (LCAT), thereby improving lipid metabolism (Ahmad, et al., 2018).

Cardiovascular Effects

Drinking Zamzam water causes transient adjustments in cardiac autonomic control, leading to increased systolic, diastolic, pulse, and mean arterial pressure within five minutes post-consumption, like ordinary mineral water. Unlike mineral water, Zamzam water uniquely increases SDRR (standard deviation of normal-to-normal heartbeats) and RMSSD (square root of the mean squared differences of successive RR intervals), reflecting enhanced parasympathetic modulation without affecting cardiac sympathetic activity (Latif, et al., 2020).

Wound Healing Properties

Moni et al. (2022) demonstrated that Zamzam water possesses potent wound-healing capabilities, achieving up to 96% healing by the 12th day in an animal model. This effect is attributed to its modulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α) and reduction in apoptosis markers (caspase-9 and caspase-3). Zinc in Zamzam water plays a critical role in protein and collagen synthesis during the healing process, making it superior to standard treatments like povidone iodine cream.

Immune System Modulation

Based on religious teachings, Zamzam water enhances immunity according to its unique chemical composition (Aini, Vera, & Truna, 2022). Essential minerals like calcium, magnesium, and fluoride play a vital role in combating inflammation and oxidative stress (Mahmoud, et al., 2020). Ibn al-Qayyim observed that many individuals experienced miraculous healing after consuming Zamzam water, suggesting its efficacy as a natural remedy (Jannah, 2018).

Viral Infections (e.g., COVID-19)

While no direct evidence exists linking Zamzam water to treating specific viral infections like COVID-19, its rich mineral content supports its use as an immune booster (Aini, Vera, & Truna, 2022). Antioxidant minerals such as selenium, strontium, and magnesium counteract arsenic effects, potentially aiding recovery from viral illnesses (Mahmoud, et al., 2020).

Figure 3. Therapeutic Benefits of Zamzam Water

Mechanisms of Action

The therapeutic effects of Zamzam water can be attributed to its unique mineral composition and physical properties:

Antioxidant Properties

Essential elements like selenium, zinc, and manganese activate antioxidant enzymes such as glutathione peroxidase, superoxide dismutase, and catalase (Wahyudi, et al., 2022; Khalid, et al., 2014). Elevated bicarbonate and alkalinity enhance detoxification and reduce oxidative stress. The alkaline nature of Zamzam water activates thiol-dependent antioxidant activity of human serum albumin, providing additional protection against oxidative stress (Mahmoud, et al., 2020; Lee, Cha, & Kim, 2000).

Anti-Inflammatory Effects

Reduction in pro-inflammatory mediators and cytokines contributes to its protective role in diabetes and cancer (El Maleky, et al., 2021; Ali, et al., 2009). Anti-inflammatory effects extend to neuronal cells, supporting neuroprotection (Abuelhaija, et al., 2023).

Aquaporin Stimulation

Zamzam water activates AQPs, improving cellular hydration and supporting vital physiological functions (Wahyudi, et al., 2022; Ali, et al., 2009).

Radiological Features

While containing low levels of uranium (U), thorium (Th), and potassium-40 (^{40}K), these radionuclides do not pose significant health risks due to their negligible quantities (Koh, et al., 2008; Arida, Mohsen, & Schöning, 2009).

Safety and Quality Assurance

Zamzam water meets or exceeds international standards for potability:

Mineral Content

All analysed elements fall within WHO guidelines, with no detectable harmful heavy metals like lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), nickel (Ni), copper (Cu), or arsenic (As) beyond permissible limits (Bhardwaj, 2023; Ali, Aminu, & Orode, 2024). Trace amounts of arsenic (19–26 ppb) and lithium have been identified but remain below risk thresholds, ensuring safety (Shomar, 2012; Moni, et al., 2022).

Microbial Growth

No microbial growth has been observed in Zamzam water due to its natural salinity and antimicrobial properties (Shomar, 2012 ; Latif, et al., 2020). Even when exposed to open air for extended periods, Zamzam water resists bacterial colonization, maintaining its purity (Moni, et al., 2022).

Isotopic Signature

Depleted $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (-10.04‰) and $\delta^2\text{H}$ (-90.36‰) values suggest ancient recharge during cooler climatic periods, reinforcing its purity and stability over millennia (Koh, et al., 2008; Al-Gamal, 2008).

Quality Control Measures

The Zamzam Studies and Research Centre (ZSRC) ensure consistent quality through advanced filtration systems and regular monitoring ("Saudi Geological Survey,," 2020).

Safety to liver and kidney

In her study on experimental animals, Al Doghaither and her colleagues concluded that the high concentrations of elements in Zamzam water do not induce hepatotoxicity or nephrotoxicity, and the water is considered safe for long-term consumption (Al Doghaither, et al., 2021).

Discussion

Several hypotheses explain the unique properties of Zamzam water:

Geological Origins

Located in the wadi Ibrahim, the well taps groundwater from diorite bedrock and wadi alluvium, facilitating prolonged water-rock interaction (Khalid, et al., 2014; Koh, et al., 2008). Magmatic CO₂ influx lowers pH, enhancing silicate mineral dissolution and enriching the water with essential ions (Koh, et al., 2008).

Crystallography and Nanotechnology

Emoto's experiments demonstrate that Zamzam water forms intricate ice crystals when exposed to prayer or sacred words, suggesting a connection between consciousness and molecular structure (Wahyudi, et al., 2022). Nano-sized silver recovery rates are higher in Zamzam water compared to other sources, indicating its potential applications in nanotechnology (Arida, Mohsen, & Schöning, 2009). Lutfiah, 2020 highlighted Emoto's observations that diluting Zamzam water with regular water retains its beneficial properties, emphasizing its exceptional nature.

Holistic Perspective

Beyond its biochemical properties, Zamzam water's efficacy depends on the user's intention, aligning with Islamic teachings (Bhardwaj, 2023; Wahyudi, et al., 2022). Cultural and religious factors influence perceptions of its therapeutic benefits, emphasizing the importance of context-specific interpretations (Aini, Vera, & Truna, 2022). The benefits of Zamzam water are mentioned in several hadiths, including one narrated by ibn Majah number 3063, which reads:

حدثنا هشام بن عمار حدثنا الوليد بن مسلم قال: قال عبد الله بن المؤمل إنه سمع أبا الزبير يقول سمعت جابر بن عبد الله يقول سمعت رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم يقول ماء زمزم لما شرب له.

Meaning: Has told us Hisham bin Ammar; have told us Al Walid bin Muslim said, Abdullah bin Mu'ammal said; that he heard Abu Az- Zubair said; I heard Jabir bin Abdullah radiallahu 'anhu, he said; I heard the Prophet may Allah bless him and grant him peace (sallallahu 'alaihi wasallam) saying: "Zamzam water (efficacious) according to the intention (purpose) to drink (by the user).

The hadith explains that Zamzam water will be beneficial depending on the intention or purpose when using it. If someone drinks it intending to be given healing for the disease he is suffering from, Allah will give him healing. If someone drinks it intending to quench their thirst, then Allah Almighty (SWT) will quench his thirst. Moreover, Allah SWT will protect it if it is intended to get protection (SUNNAH.COM).

When we look to the duties that pilgrims do during Hajj and health challenge they face, and see the properties of Zamzam water mentioned above we find that Zamzam water was fashioned to support them through that journey.

Conclusion

This systematic review confirms the exceptional qualities of Zamzam water, supported by scientific evidence and religious beliefs. Its rich mineral composition, alkaline pH, and absence of harmful contaminants make it safe and beneficial for consumption. Key therapeutic benefits include improved glycaemic control, renal protective effects, cancer prevention, enhanced dental health, support for reproductive systems, cardiovascular regulation, neurological protection, wound-healing properties, and now, evidence of its safety despite concerns about arsenic and nitrate content.

While current research provides valuable insights, further studies are warranted to explore its full potential, especially regarding rare-earth elements, metalloids, long-term health impacts, and interactions with modern diseases like viral infections. Additionally, efforts should focus on standardizing bottling practices to ensure global distribution without compromising quality. Addressing concerns about trace heavy metals remains critical for maintaining safety. Understanding the interplay between its unique properties and cultural/religious contexts will deepen our appreciation of its holistic benefits. Zamzam water would be the best drink and support ever during Hajj time.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Ethical Statement

No ethical approval was required as this study did not involve human participants or laboratory animals.

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